

Teacher Change and Interpersonal Communication Skills among Elementary Teachers

RUBELYN T. BASILAN

Master of Arts in Education Major in School Administration and Supervision, East West Mindanao Colleges INC.
Kamasi, Ampatuan, Maguindanao

Teacher, Camahual Elementary School, Division of Davao Occidental, Department of Education, Philippines, 8011

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15242368>

Published Date: 18-April-2025

Abstract: This study is aimed to find out the relationship between teacher change and interpersonal communication skills among elementary teachers. This study utilized the non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive technique involving teachers in Sarangani District of Davao Occidental Division, Philippines. The study was conducted on the second semester of School Year 2024-2025. Research instruments on teacher change and interpersonal communication skills among elementary teachers were used as source of data. Using mean and pearson-r as statistical tools to treat the data, the study showed the following results: the study found to exhibit a very high level of teacher change; there is a very high level of interpersonal communication skills among elementary teachers; there is a significant relationship between teacher change and interpersonal communication skills among elementary teachers. This implies that the higher the teacher change, the higher is the interpersonal communication skills among elementary teachers. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between teacher change and interpersonal communication skills among elementary teachers was rejected.

Keywords: teacher change, interpersonal communication skills, elementary teachers, school administration and supervision.

I. INTRODUCTION

Teaching is synonymous to giving instruction. The key to making students effectively understand the lesson lies in the teacher's communication skills. However, there are a number of teachers who are unable to express themselves well before the students. They suffer from speech impediments and giving instructions appear vague and unintelligible. Others are talking too fast that students start to miss important points in the instruction resulting to poor learning outcomes among the students (İhtiyaroğlu, 2019).

Teacher change is indispensable in advancing the instructional competence of teachers specifically in the aspect of communication. It increases teacher's knowledge in integrating different technologies for teaching language skills. In effect, this brings professional change in instructional delivery of teachers while it develops their communicative competence. Through teacher change, communicating the learning concepts to students has become efficient. This association is apparent in the ways teachers manifest confidence in their pedagogical roles knowing that their change is anchored in a solid foundation paving the way to converse these to their students (Murtiningsih, Kristiawan & Lian, 2019).

In the local setting, at the time of the study, it is noted that there are teachers who lack the ability to articulate significant concepts of the lessons. On the other hand, there are also teachers who fail to highlight important theory and model in the discussion of the lesson due to stuttering. Other teachers cannot teach well due to inappropriate communication skills that results to their poor understanding of the lessons and instructions

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 12, Issue 2, pp: (44-47), Month: March - April 2025, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

To date, there has no study conducted in the local context regarding the correlation between teacher change and communication skills among public elementary language teachers. While the issues on problem on communication competence of teachers continue to be unaddressed, there is also no available institutionalized program in the division to help teacher enhance their communication competence. Undeniably, the need to give special attention to this concern is important in order to increase students' learning outcome. It is on this reason that this research is conceptualized in order to explore on the given topic and to look into the veracity of the presented problems on teacher's communication competence.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE**Statement of the Problem**

The main thrust of this study is to determine the relationship between teacher change and interpersonal communication skills among elementary teachers. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of teacher change knowledge in terms of:
 - 1.1 knowledge;
 - 2.2 personality, and
 - 2.3 skills?
2. What is the level of interpersonal communication skills among public school language teacher in terms of:
 - 2.1 sending clear messages;
 - 2.2 listening;
 - 2.3 giving and getting feedback, and
 - 2.4 handling emotional interactions?
3. Is there significant relationship between teacher change and interpersonal communication skills among public school language teacher?

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses will be treated at 0.05 level of significance.

There is no significant relationship between teacher change and interpersonal communication skills among public school language teacher.

III. METHODOLOGY**Research Design**

This study utilized a quantitative correlational design is a type of non-experimental research design used to determine whether and to what degree a relationship exists between two or more quantifiable variables. This study will find out the significance of the relationship between teacher change and interpersonal communication skills among elementary teachers.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools were used in the analysis of data.

Mean. This was used to determine the level of teacher change and interpersonal communication skills among elementary teachers.

Pearson *r*. This was used to determine the significance of the relationship between teacher change and interpersonal communication skills among elementary teachers.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**Level of Teacher Change**

Shown in Table 1 is the level of level of teacher change with an overall mean of 4.09 with a descriptive equivalent of very high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

 Vol. 12, Issue 2, pp: (44-47), Month: March - April 2025, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com
Table I. Level of Teacher Change

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Knowledge	4.06	Very High
Personality	4.10	Very High
Skills	4.11	Very High
Overall	4.09	Very High

Among the enumerated indicators, skills has the highest mean rating with a mean score of 4.11 or very high, followed by personality with a mean score of 4.20 or very high, and knowledge with a mean score of 4.06 or very high. The result of this study is supported by the statement of Sancar, Atal & Deryakulu (2021) who stated that as the learning landscape continues to evolve, teachers need to get along with the changes. To be relevant in the current teaching and learning situation means being able to adapt to the changes that have been taking place in the learning environment. Today, only those teachers who are able to perfectly blend with the curriculum can create a meaningful classroom learning experiences for the students to take advantage of an increase level of learning outcome.

Level of Interpersonal Communication Skills among Elementary Teachers

Presented in Table 2 are the ratings of interpersonal communication skills among elementary teachers. Computations revealed an overall mean score of 4.11 or very high rating indicating that the said respondents always manifested. Among the enumerated indicators, handling emotional interactions ranked the highest with a mean score of 4.15 or very high, sending clear messages, 4.10 or very high, listening, 4.12 or very high, and getting and giving feedback, 4.08 or very high.

The result of the study is aligned with the statement of Urbanek, Losa, Wieczorek-Kosmala, Hlaváček & Lokaj (2023) who believed that interpersonal communication skills are the abilities to effectively communicate ideas through face to face communication. Every day, teachers give instructions to students and explain concepts for students to understand the lesson and eventually develop mastery. The success and failure of teaching is dependent on the ability of teachers to convey idea through interpersonal communication.

Table II. Level of Interpersonal Communication Skills

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Sending Clear Messages	4.10	Very High
Listening	4.12	Very High
Giving and Getting Feedback	4.08	Very High
Handling Emotional Interactions	4.15	Very High
Overall	4.11	Very High

This is also aligned with the view of Schmid Mast, Kleinlogel, Tur & Bachmann (2018) who said that teachers know exactly how it is important to communicate the lessons to students. With the goal of making the students master the competency, teachers have to exhaust all means to give the best learning experiences to students. The most important means for teacher is to effectively communicate to students the concepts and ideas underlying the lesson. The passing and failure of the students to the day's lesson is truly dependent to the teacher's ability to communicate the lesson to the students.

The need for teachers to possess a good sense of interpersonal communication is a must. As teaching profession entails communication and giving instructions, teachers must constantly evaluate their skill on this aspect in order to be successful in teaching. Students can learn best with teachers who are good at explaining lessons. Similarly, students will easily understand instruction when it is well explained (Anggunsari & Wahyuni, 2023; Moradi, 2020).

Significance on the Relationship between Teacher Change and Interpersonal Communication Skills among Elementary Teachers

Illustrated in Table 3 were the results of the test of relationship between variables involved in the study. The overall correlation had a computed value of 0.105 with a probability value of $p < 0.01$ which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between teacher change and interpersonal communication skills among elementary teachers is rejected.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

 Vol. 12, Issue 2, pp: (44-47), Month: March - April 2025, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com
Table III. Significance on the Relationship between Teacher Change and Interpersonal Communication Skills among Elementary Teachers

Pair	Variables	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Decision on Ho
IV and DV	Teacher Change and Interpersonal Communication Skills among Elementary Teachers	0.105	0.000	Reject

learners during their most formative years, the ability to respond effectively to change is crucial. One of the key factors that influences a teacher's ability to navigate change is their interpersonal communication skills. These skills play a vital role in how teachers collaborate, support one another, and implement new strategies successfully.

The relationship between teacher change and interpersonal communication skills among elementary teachers is strong and deeply interconnected. As teachers face new challenges and expectations, their ability to communicate clearly, listen actively, and collaborate effectively determines how smoothly they can adapt and grow. By fostering these skills and creating a culture of open communication, schools can support their teachers in becoming more confident, connected, and capable change agents, ultimately benefiting students and the entire educational community (Hamm & Mousseau, 2023).

V. CONCLUSION

Based from the findings of the study, conclusions are drawn in this section. The study found to exhibit a very high level of teacher change. This means that the provisions relating to teacher change is always manifested.

The study revealed a very high level of interpersonal communication skills among elementary teachers. This indicates that the provisions relating to interpersonal communication skills among elementary teachers are embodied in the item is always manifested.

The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship teacher change and interpersonal communication skills among elementary teachers. This implies that the higher the level of teacher change, the higher is the interpersonal communication skills among elementary teachers. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between teacher change and interpersonal communication skills among elementary teachers was rejected.

REFERENCES

- [1] Anggunsari, P., & Wahyuni, S. (2023). Direct Written Corrective Feedback for Tenth Graders Recount Text: Adequate Practice to Boost Sentential Accuracy. *Journal of English Teaching*, 9(3), 310-322.
- [2] Hamm, J. E., & Mousseau, A. D. (2023). Predicting parent trust based on professionals' communication skills. *Education Sciences*, 13(4), 350.
- [3] İhtiyaroğlu, N. (2019). Analysis of the predictive role of teachers' effective communication skills and motivation levels on classroom management profiles. *Journal of Education and E-Learning Research*, 6(1), 17-25.
- [4] Murtiningsih, M., Kristiawan, M., & Lian, B. (2019). The correlation between supervision of headmaster and interpersonal communication with work ethos of the teacher. *European Journal of Education Studies*.
- [5] Sancar, R., Atal, D., & Deryakulu, D. (2021). A new framework for teachers' professional development. *Teaching and teacher education*, 101, 103305.
- [6] Schmid Mast, M., Kleinlogel, E. P., Tur, B., & Bachmann, M. (2018). The future of interpersonal skills development: Immersive virtual reality training with virtual humans. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 29(2), 125-141.
- [7] Urbanek, A., Losa, A., Wiczorek-Kosmala, M., Hlaváček, K., & Lokaj, A. (2023). Did the Quality of Digital Communication Skills in Education Improve after the Pandemic? Evidence from HEIs. *Sustainability*, 15(15), 11878.